

OCEAN:ICE News – November 2024

OCEAN:ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN:ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System.

OCEAN:ICE News is a monthly newsletter updating about the project's progress, results, and other exciting events! Be sure to follow us on LinkedIn to stay informed.

Welcome!

Welcome to November's edition of OCEAN:ICE News, celebrating 2 years of OCEAN:ICE! We're excited to bring you the latest updates from the OCEAN:ICE community.

In this issue, you'll meet our featured researcher of the month and catch up on key activities, including articles on the KOPRI Annual Symposium, Arctic Circle Assembly, Ocean Best Practices System Workshop, as well as the SO-CHIC meeting. You can catch up on our Climate Coffees. Don't forget to mark your calendars for the upcoming Weddell Sea Dronning Maud Land working group workshop and more exciting events.

We hope you enjoy exploring this month's updates, and we look forward to sharing more in December!

2 Years of OCEAN:ICE

At the start of November we celebrated 2 years of OCEAN:ICE!

The project started on the 1st of November 2022 and will run for 4 years until 31st October 2026. We are halfway through our 4-year scientific journey.

Watch the video on the [website](#).

Researcher in the Spotlight: Xabier Davila

Check out our latest 'Researcher in the Spotlight' feature on Xabier Davila, an oceanography Postdoc at [NORCE](#).

Read the feature on Xabier [here](#).

Stay tuned for more features from our Research Team in OCEAN:ICE.

Catching up on the Latest OCEAN:ICE Activities

OCEAN:ICE at KOPRI Annual Symposium 2024

OCEAN:ICE took part in the KOPRI Polar Symposium in Songdo, Incheon on September 30th-1st October 2024. [Anna Wählin](#) from OCEAN:ICE attended this meeting. OCEAN:ICE gave a seminar in session S3 'Changes in the Antarctic Ocean and its interaction with ice sheets'.

The theme for the 29th Polar symposium was 'Scientific advances based on Antarctic Jang Bogo Station over the last 10 years'. You can read the full article [here](#).

Poster session and lively discussion

OCEAN:ICE at Arctic Circle Assembly 2024

The OCEAN:ICE attended Arctic Circle assembly in Reykjavik, Iceland on 19-20 October 2024. This was a meeting place for inspiring talks, discussions, and true interactions between stakeholders, policy makers, entrepreneurs, and scientists, working in and with the Arctic.

This year the ACA launched a new initiative called the “Polar Dialogue”. Chaired by the former Prime Minister of Iceland Katrín Jakobsdóttir and Director of AWI Antje Boetius. In a typical scientific conference, we would have scientific talks and posters. In contrast, during the ACA we scientists disseminate our knowledge by actively interacting in the dialogues, such as the Polar Dialogue.

Read more on the [website](#).

Panel at the Arctic Circle Assembly

Ocean Best Practices System Workshop (OBPS WSVIII) 2024

On the 17th of October Andrew Meijers presented online at the 8th Ocean Best Practices System Workshop, in the Ocean-Climate nexus session. He presented on novel ocean observations and their important role in defining and monitoring global tipping points. The presentation drew heavily on OCEAN:ICE work, both observational and modelling, and emphasised the importance of developing effective observing systems for Antarctic ice sheet ocean interactions.

This presentation can be accessed here: <https://zenodo.org/records/13969379>

The image is a promotional poster for the OBPS Workshop VIII. It features a blue background with a pattern of white dots. In the upper left, there is a logo for 'Ocean best practices' and a smaller logo for '2021-2030'. The main text is centered and reads: 'OBPS Workshop VIII / 14-18 October, 2024 [ONLINE]', 'Ocean-Climate Nexus - Importance of Ocean Observing for Tipping Points, and the downstream effects of Tipping Points.', and '17 Oct | 15:00 - 16:30 UTC'. There is a circular inset image on the right showing a diver underwater. At the bottom, there is a small line of text: 'Background Images: ian/Photo: Tony Matheis (AP/Photo Eye) and Stuart Webb (Shutterstock) / Ocean Image Bank'.

OCEAN:ICE at SO-CHIC Final Meeting

The [SO-CHIC](#) final meeting was held in Paris over 28-30th of October. SO-CHIC focuses on Antarctic circulation and its impact on heat and carbon, with a particular focus on the Weddell sea.

Several members of OCEAN:ICE took part in the meeting, and presented ongoing OCEAN:ICE science that follows, directly in some cases, from the SO-CHIC project.

Read the article [here](#).

OCEAN:ICE Milestones and Deliverables Submitted

The OCEAN:ICE community has been busy recently submitting various deliverables and milestones:

- D2.2 '[AUV Observations Under the Sea-Ice Around Grounded Icebergs](#)'
- D1.7 '[Evaluation of Control FESOM Hindcast \(1979-present\)](#)'
- D2.3 '[Ship and AUV observations near /within a warm ice-shelf cavity \(D2.3\)](#)'
- MS30 '[Analysis of Historical Precipitation Extremes in Downscaled ERA5 RCM Output from Polar CORDEX](#)'

The progress and results of OCEAN:ICE are published in deliverables and milestone reports.

In order to keep up with the OCEAN:ICE deliverables and milestones, visit our [website](#) and stay tuned on our social media channels.

Climate Coffees

Since its relaunch the [Climate Coffee series](#) has been in full swing. If you've missed any of the recent ones, don't you worry, you may catch up [here](#).

Climate Coffee

Upcoming Events

SOOS Weddell Sea Dronning Maud Land Working Group Workshop

The SOOS Weddell Sea Dronning Maud Land working group workshop is presently being held online (7-8th November). It brings together Southern Ocean scientists with an interest in this region in a multidisciplinary discussion about what work is and will be undertaken in the region and identifying emerging science questions. A number of OCEAN:ICE members are taking part and presenting, and the session is being co-convened by WP1 co-lead Markus Janout. Andrew Meijers will present a short talk on OCEAN:ICE activities in the region. The meeting runs from 0900-1200 on Thursday and Friday CET.

Happening Soon

OCEAN:ICE will be at these upcoming events. Will you also be there? Let us know!

- 11-15 November 2024, [Joint Meeting IQUOD/GTSPP/SOOP/XBT Science](#), Bologna
- 27-30 January 2025, [Arctic Frontiers 2025: Beyond Borders](#), Tromsø, Norway

Do you know of any exciting events that OCEAN:ICE should be a part of? Shoot us a mail at oceanice.eu@gmail.com.

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Stay up to date with OCEAN:ICE on our following channels:

www.ocean-ice.eu

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/euoceanice/>

https://twitter.com/OCEANICE_EU

<https://fediscience.org/@OceanIceEU>

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Who is OCEAN:ICE?

OCEAN:ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System. OCEAN:ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN:ICE focus on understanding how the Antarctic ice sheet and the surrounding Southern Ocean influence our global climate and reduce the level of uncertainty around how much the Antarctic ice sheet will melt in the coming centuries. OCEAN:ICE considers the critical role of feedbacks between ocean circulation, ice sheet change and tipping points and the global climate. [Find out more](#)

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